

Estimating Laser Transit Anemometry Noise Performance Capabilities

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ABSTRACT

Concepts and associated algorithms for the extraction of two-dimensional flow information from laser transit anemometry (LTA) data sets are described and subjected to a detailed evaluation. Previous evaluations concentrated on determining the accuracy of the basic processing methods using correlogram ensembles containing no additional background noise due to spurious correlations. The present work attempts to extend the evaluation to include data ensembles containing 0.0, 5.0, 10.0, and 20.0% background noise levels in the constituent correlograms. The results of these evaluations indicate that for turbulence levels of up to 10.0% the processing system is able to accurately extract the necessary flow parameters from the LTA data sets. Specifically, mean velocity magnitude and flow angle are measureable to within +2.0% for turbulence intensity levels of up to 14.0% and background noise levels as mentioned above. Standard deviations are measureable to within +10.0% over a turbulence range of 3.0% - 10.0% and the same noise levels. The correlation coefficient between the u and v components of velocity is measureable to within a few percent for coefficients greater than 0.4. However, for values of correlation coefficient less than 0.4, the accuracy of the measurements is noticeably worse due to the geometrical method employed to determine the higher order moment flow parameters. These results indicate that the algorithms described here have applications in fluid flow surveys. However, care must be used to minimize the errors and provide a proper interpretation of the results.

INTRODUCTION

Research programs at Langley such as the National Aero-Space Plane (NASP) are becoming increasingly dependent on having available accurate flow diagnostic information to validate computational codes describing the model flow fields presented by these programs. It is important that maximum information be derived from data collected by instruments used to perform these flow field diagnostics. In recent tests a Mie-scattering based laser transit anemometry (LTA) system has been employed to survey supersonic flow fields as part of these programs [1]. Due to recent research in LTA acquisition and analysis techniques more information may be obtained from the data collected during these tests than was previously possible. R. Schodl for example has developed a rapid method of data acquisition and analysis based on using marginal distributions which is capable of measuring two orthogonal components

of mean velocity and turbulence intensity with an LTA system [2]. Also, laser transit anemometers capable of making three component measurements have been introduced [3] as have new methods of optical discrimination based on pairs of beams as described by M. Wernet and R. Edwards [4].

In 1984, W. Mayo and A. Smart proposed a data acquisition and analysis system for laser transit anemometry which would extract from LTA data sets obtained in a plane normal to the optical axis of the instrument two orthogonal components of mean velocity and standard deviation as well as the associated correlation coefficient [5]. The analysis method is based on estimating the probability density function (PDF) for the velocity vector at the measurement point in the flow field. Although this method of LTA data analysis has been described in detail theoretically, few quantitative analyses had been performed until now to evaluate the procedures for robustness, precision, and accuracy. It is the purpose of this paper to describe the results of a continuing detailed evaluation and testing of a modified version of Mayo and Smart's LTA data analysis system using a Monte Carlo based LTA simulation system.

Previous work using the LTA simulator concentrated on evaluating the analysis system using LTA data sets consisting of ensembles of cross correlation functions (correlograms) containing no background noise [6]. This paper presents an extension of the previous work to include test data sets containing various levels of background noise in the constituent correlograms. Through these test cases the noise performance capabilities of the LTA system to accurately measure the desired flow parameters will be examined.

LTA DATA ACQUISITION DESCRIPTION

Basic Concepts

The basic concept of laser transit anemometry is to measure the transit time of seed particles in the flow as they cross the foci of a pair of laser beams. The transit time of an individual particle, τ_i , in conjunction with the known beam separation, s , provides a measurement of the velocity, v_i , of the particle by

$$v_i = \frac{s}{\tau_i} \quad (1)$$

Assuming that the particle accurately tracks the flow field, v_i is a measure of the flow velocity at the measurement point.

The beams are rotated about an axis equidistant from and parallel to the two beams. This ability to rotate the two beams allows for the determination of flow angle. For the system to be simulated here, the beams are focused to form two Gaussian waists approximately 30 μm in diameter at a focal distance of 900 mm, and are separated by 1230 μm . The depth of focus of the beams is given by

$$z_o = \frac{\pi \omega_o^2}{\lambda} \quad (2)$$

where z_o is the focal depth, ω_o is the Gaussian waist radius, λ is the laser wavelength (514.5 nm), and it is assumed that the Rayleigh range criteria for defining the focal depth is used. Using equation (2), the depth of focus for the given configuration of the system is 2442.4 μm . The parameters given above are used in all simulation cases presented in this paper.

To detect particles as they traverse one of the foci of the instrument, the scattered light from particles is collected around the annulus of the transmission optics and relayed to a photomultiplier connected to a filter-discriminator/pulse-center detector circuit. This circuit produces TTL level pulses whenever the PMT signal exceeds a preset threshold level. Thus, as particles pass through the sample volume, a series of pulses are produced on two separate channels, one for each beam. The method used to extract transit time information consists of computing the discrete cross correlation function in real time, $r_{xy}(\tau)$, between the input pulse streams occurring on the two channels, $x(t)$ and $y(t)$. This discrete correlation function is given by

$$r_{xy}(\tau) = \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} x(t_i) y(t_i + \tau) \quad (3)$$

and is represented as a correlogram with 256 discrete "bins" (or channels) with each successive bin representing a delay time $\tau_i = i\Delta\tau$.

Flow Field Model

The analysis system is built on the basic assumption that a two-dimensional flow field may be described by a Gaussian or normal bivariate model whose moments include mean velocity, turbulence defined as the root mean square fluctuations on two orthogonal components, and a correlation component. From this Gaussian model, the probability density function (PDF) defined in a u, v coordinate system for the velocity vector at the LTA system measurement point can be written as

$$P(u, v) = \frac{1}{2\pi\sigma_u\sigma_v\sqrt{1-\rho^2}} \text{EXP} \left[\frac{-1}{2(1-\rho^2)} \left(\frac{(u-\bar{u})^2}{\sigma_u^2} - \frac{2\rho(u-\bar{u})(v-\bar{v})}{\sigma_u\sigma_v} + \frac{(v-\bar{v})^2}{\sigma_v^2} \right) \right] \quad (4)$$

The mean flow velocity and mean flow angle are defined by

$$V = (\bar{u}^2 + \bar{v}^2)^{1/2} \quad (5)$$

and

$$\bar{\varphi} = \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{\bar{v}}{\bar{u}} \right) \quad (6)$$

where \bar{u} and \bar{v} are the mean velocities along the u and v components, respectively. The RMS velocity fluctuations along the u component, σ_u , and along the v component, σ_v , are defined by

$$\sigma_u = \left[\overline{(u-\bar{u})^2} \right]^{1/2}, \quad \sigma_v = \left[\overline{(v-\bar{v})^2} \right]^{1/2} \quad (7)$$

The quantity ρ is the correlation coefficient defined by

$$\rho = \frac{\overline{(u-\bar{u})(v-\bar{v})}}{\sigma_u\sigma_v} \quad (8)$$

A plot of $P(u, v)$ for a typical set of flow conditions is shown in Figure 1.

Note that the LTA instrument does not in itself make measurements in the (u, v) domain of velocity space but rather in the (τ, φ) domain of measurement space. This is shown by considering that the LTA system is only able to measure the transit times of particles which have trajectory angles within the angle of acceptance of the instrument centered around the beam orientation ϕ . The velocity of individual particles is computed through equation (1). To determine the probability density function in the (τ, φ) domain, the (u, v) domain PDF must be multiplied by a Jacobian factor relating the PDFs in the two domains [7]:

$$P(\tau, \varphi) = \frac{s^2}{\tau} P(u, v) \quad (9)$$

with the following substitutions made:

$$u = \frac{s \cos \varphi}{\tau} \quad v = \frac{s \sin \varphi}{\tau} \quad (10)$$

Measurement Procedure

The procedure employed for collecting two-dimensional flow data from the LTA system is to orient the two beams at seven to thirteen different angles with respect to the estimated mean flow direction (which many times must be determined by trial and error) and compute the discrete cross correlation function given in (3) (Figure 2a). Note that due to the turbulent fluctuations of the flow vector at the measurement point only those particles which have a direction within the angle of acceptance of the two beams ($\phi \pm 0.9$ degrees for the geometry given previously) will be measured. In effect each correlogram consists of a thin slice through the PDF in the (τ, φ) domain whose thickness depends on the angle of acceptance of the instrument. By rotating the beams to slightly different orientations around the estimated mean flow direction, the additional correlograms represent different slices through

the PDF. The ensemble of correlograms are combined together to form an estimate of the PDF in the (τ, ϕ) domain .

LTA DATA ANALYSIS DESCRIPTION

The LTA data analysis system is composed of four distinct steps:

1. The ensemble of correlograms in the (τ, ϕ) domain is filtered and the average background level present in each correlogram is subtracted out to remove as much noise as possible.
2. The first order statistical moments are extracted analytically from the (τ, ϕ) domain data set through the application of direct estimators.
3. The ensemble of correlograms in the (τ, ϕ) domain is transformed to the (u, v) domain.
4. The second order statistical moments are extracted geometrically from the PDF estimate in the (u, v) domain.

Each of the four steps is distinct from the others and will be described separately.

Noise Removal Procedures

The first step in the data analysis process is the removal of noise from the individual correlograms in the (τ, ϕ) domain ensemble. Noise is defined here as the presence of spurious correlations in the individual correlograms. To filter a correlogram, a self-adaptive digital filter incorporating a triangular Parzen weighting function is used. The average background level, b , is first estimated by averaging the correlogram between the third bin and the bin nearest to 0.6 times the peak bin. The total data in the correlogram, Q , is determined by adding up all the events in all the bins. The half-width of the filter is then computed by

$$HW = \text{ROUND} \left(\frac{\beta(Q - nb)}{2(h - b)} \right) , \quad (11)$$

where the operation ROUND makes HW an integer. β is a selected empirical constant which provides control over the broadening induced by the filter while n is the number of bins in the correlogram. Having computed HW, the filter is now applied to the original correlogram. Each data point $Y(k)$ in the function is replaced by a triangularly weighted average over the set of data points from locations $k-HW$ to $k+HW$ using

$$Y(k) \leftarrow \frac{1}{HW} \sum_{j=-HW}^{j=+HW} \left(1 - \left| \frac{k-j}{HW} \right| \right) \cdot Y(j) . \quad (12)$$

After filtering, a new estimate of the background noise is made by computing the average channel height over the first 20% of the bins in the correlogram and over the last 20% of bins. The greater of these two averages is taken to be the background estimate which is then subtracted from the cor-

relogram. Note that this background removal process assumes that the non-spurious correlations in the correlogram do not occupy more than the central 50% of the correlogram, thereby limiting the effective turbulence intensity that can be measured. Higher turbulence intensities can be measured, but an estimate of the background noise must be made by visual inspection of the correlogram and then subtracted out.

The final step in the noise removal process is to truncate the outliers to remove any background that remains beyond the bounds of the central correlogram distribution. The truncation limits are defined to be the bins on either side of the peak of the function which first fall to zero. The correlogram is zeroed out beyond these limits.

Extraction of First Order Statistics

The first order statistical moments of mean velocity and mean flow angle are extracted analytically from the ensemble of filtered correlograms in the (τ, ϕ) domain through the application of direct estimators. These estimators incorporate the Jacobian term described previously. The direct estimator used to compute the mean velocity is given by

$$V = \frac{s}{\Delta\tau} \frac{\sum_j \sum_i i^{-1} \eta_i(\phi_j)}{\sum_j \sum_i \eta_i(\phi_j)} , \quad (13)$$

while the estimator for the mean flow angle is given by

$$\bar{\varphi} = \frac{\sum_j \sum_i \phi_j \eta_i(\phi_j)}{\sum_j \sum_i \eta_i(\phi_j)} , \quad (14)$$

where ϕ_j is the j^{th} angular beam orientation, $\eta_i(\phi_j)$ is the number of events in the i^{th} bin of the j^{th} correlogram, s is the beam separation, and $\Delta\tau$ is the delay increment between successive bins in the correlograms. Note that all correlograms in an ensemble have the same value of $\Delta\tau$.

It is important to note that when using the direct estimators given in equations (13) and (14) it is assumed that enough correlograms have been taken at sufficiently separated beam orientations to adequately bracket the peak of the PDF in the (u, v) domain. If the peak of the PDF is not well bracketed, then a significant bias is introduced in the first order statistics.

PDF Transformation

Before the second order moments of standard deviation and correlation coefficient are extracted geometrically from the estimated PDF function, the nonlinearity between the (τ, ϕ) and (u, v) domains must be taken into account. As stated previously, this nonlinearity is a first order inverse relationship between time and velocity given by equation (1). To remove this nonlinearity, the (τ, ϕ) ensemble of correlograms are transformed to the (u, v) domain through application of equation (9) by

$$P(u,v) = \frac{\tau^3}{s^2} P(\tau, \varphi) \quad (15)$$

The correlograms are then converted to a polar representation as shown in Figure 2b.

Extraction of Second Order Statistics

To determine σ_u , σ_v , and ρ , the PDF is estimated geometrically. Each correlogram in the (u,v) domain can be thought of as a slice through the PDF at an angle ϕ_j . Thus any operations performed on the PDF affect all correlograms in the ensemble. To estimate the shape of the PDF, a cross section parallel to the u, v plane is obtained from the PDF at a specified height H_0/e^{-b} , where H_0 is the peak height of the entire ensemble of correlograms and b is a constant. Normally the height is set at the $\frac{H_0}{\sqrt{e}}$ level due to the gradient of the PDF being maximum at this level. From this cross section a set of points representing contributions from individual correlograms in the ensemble is formed through which a least squares fit of an ellipse is performed. This type of fitting relies on the Gaussian PDF assumption. Note that typically all the correlograms present in the ensemble are not used to derive the ellipse, for correlograms defining the edges of the PDF have a peak height below the height of the cross section, and thus are not represented in the ellipse. This effect gives rise to a noise rejection capability in the extraction of the second order statistics because outlying correlograms of the ensemble are typically of the poorest quality.

Once the ellipse has been defined it is projected onto the (u,v) plane, illustrated in Figure 3. It can be shown [8] that σ_u and σ_v can be found from the points on the ellipse at which the tangents of the ellipse are parallel to the coordinate axes; i.e.,

$$\sigma_u^2 = \frac{(\bar{u}-\bar{u})^2}{2b} \quad \text{when } \frac{du}{du} = \infty \quad (16)$$

and

$$\sigma_v^2 = \frac{(\bar{v}-\bar{v})^2}{2b} \quad \text{when } \frac{dv}{dv} = 0 \quad (17)$$

while the correlation coefficient ρ can be found from either of the points of intersection of the ellipse with the u-axis when $\bar{\varphi}$ is set to zero, as in

$$\rho = \left[1 - \frac{(\bar{u}-\bar{u})^2}{2b \sigma_u^2} \right]^{1/2} \quad \text{when } \bar{\varphi}=0 \quad (18)$$

Occasionally the least squares fitting procedure will fail to produce an ellipse due to the chosen height of the cross section being too high. In these cases too few correlograms are used for the fit. Therefore, a test is performed to determine if the coefficients found in carrying out the least squares fit do indeed satisfy the criteria for an ellipse. Normally the selection of a lower height for the cross section will enable the fitting routine to produce a correct ellipse. However, in low

signal to noise ratio regimes it is sometimes impossible to adequately choose the height so that enough correlograms are used in the fit while at the same time ensuring that a minimum of noise present along the edges of the PDF is used.

LTA SIMULATION DESCRIPTION

Assumptions

The LTA simulation system is based on Monte Carlo simulation techniques and gives individual particles random trajectories through a model of the LTA system's sample volume. If a particle successfully traverses both beams of the system then its transit time is computed and placed in the proper bin of a histogram corresponding to the current angular setting of the beams with respect to the mean flow direction. Several simplifying assumptions have been made to reduce the complexity of the sample volume model:

1. The beams are represented as Gaussian waists with the loci of constant intensities represented as ellipsoids in space, as shown in Figure 4. The ellipsoid representing a constant intensity for each beam defines a hard threshold within which all particles are detected while particles passing outside the ellipsoid are ignored. Note that the amount of scattered light from particles and resultant PMT output waveforms are not computed at this time with the current model.
2. All particles passing through the sample volume are monodispersed. This assumption is necessary to maintain consistency with assumption 1 because particles of various sizes scatter different amounts of light, thereby invalidating the assumption of fixed intensity ellipsoids in space.
3. The transit time histograms are assumed to be equivalent in form to the correlograms generated by the actual instrument.
4. Background noise present in correlograms due to spurious correlations is assumed to be a separate Poisson distribution process which can be applied to the base histograms. This Poisson distributed noise is added linearly to the histograms.

Simulation Process

The simulation is performed by orienting the beams to a given angle with respect to the desired mean flow direction, sending through the sample volume a specified number of particles, N_p , and generating a sample histogram for this angular orientation. The beams are then reoriented to a different angle and a new histogram constructed. Histograms are constructed for as many different angular orientations as are necessary to adequately define the PDF function for the flow. The particles have random initial positions within the first beam, and random u, and v velocity components. It is assumed that only one particle is present in the sample volume at a time.

To determine N_p , a histogram ensemble height is specified. The central histogram, which corresponds to the optimum beam orientation with respect to the flow direction, is

always simulated first, and a running total of the number of particles required to achieve the histogram ensemble height is maintained. For all subsequent histograms in the ensemble, the same number of particles is sent through the sample volume as were required for the central histogram. This arrangement represents a time independent flow field seeding situation where degradation in companion histograms of the ensemble is due to changes in the orientation of the two beams with respect to the flow field mean direction and not due to changes in seeding rate.

For the simulation cases considered here, only two components of the flow (u and v) are assumed to be nonzero, which simplifies the generation of particle velocities using an algorithm described by D. Knuth [9]. For two dimensional flows, the u component of velocity for each particle, u_i , can be written as

$$u_i = \bar{u} + \sigma_u \chi_1 \quad , \quad (19)$$

where χ_1 is a Gaussian random number with zero mean and standard deviation of one and \bar{u} is the mean velocity in the u direction. The v component of velocity for each particle, v_i , can be written as

$$v_i = \bar{v} + \sigma_v [\rho \chi_1 + \sqrt{1-\rho^2} \chi_2] \quad , \quad (20)$$

where χ_2 is a Gaussian random number with zero mean and standard deviation of one and \bar{v} is the mean velocity in the v direction. Equation (20) directly couples the correlation coefficient between the u_i and v_i components of velocity.

For each particle sent through the sample volume model, the coordinates of the particle's closest approach to the axis of each beam must be determined. For particles that fall within the ellipsoid of constant intensity for the downstream beam (by definition all particles pass through the upstream beam), these closest approach coordinates are used to compute the beam transit time for the particle using

$$t_i = \frac{[(x_2 - x_1)^2 + (y_2 - y_1)^2]^{1/2}}{|V_i|} \quad , \quad (21)$$

where (x_1, y_1) and (x_2, y_2) are the coordinates of closest approach to the axis of each beam and $|V_i|$ is the magnitude of the particle's velocity. The i^{th} bin in the current correlogram is then incremented by one. The proper bin to increment is chosen by

$$n_i = \text{ROUND} \left(\frac{t_i}{\Delta \tau} \right) \quad , \quad (22)$$

where the ROUND function takes the greatest integer less than the argument in parentheses, and $\Delta \tau$ is the delay increment between successive bins in the correlogram.

Noise Model

It is assumed for the purposes of this simulation study that the background noise present in correlograms due to spurious correlations may be modeled as a separate Poisson distributed process. This noise is added linearly to the cor-

relograms generated in the initial pass of the simulator. Mathematically, this can be represented as

$$r(\tau) = r'(\tau) + \eta(\tau) \quad , \quad (23)$$

where $r(\tau)$ is the simulated correlogram with added background noise, $r'(\tau)$ is the simulated correlogram from the first pass of the simulator, and $\eta(\tau)$ is Poisson distributed background noise modeled as

$$\frac{e^{-\lambda \tau} (\lambda \tau)^{h_n}}{h_n!} \quad , \quad (24)$$

where h_n is the chosen background height in the correlograms and λ is a rate constant to provide dimensionless quantities. Equation (24) represents the probability of obtaining h_n spurious correlations in a bin of the correlogram representing a time interval τ . Figure 5 illustrates the addition of background noise to a typical correlogram generated with the first pass of the simulator.

Note that the same background level is simulated in all correlograms of the data ensemble regardless of angular position. In actual LTA measurements it is possible for the background level to vary as the angular orientation of the beams is changed due to the introduction of stray light such as flare into the receiver. This effect is most noticeable when performing flow field measurements close to model surfaces.

Simulation Statistics

The simulator maintains two sets of statistics on the particles passing through the simulator for a particular run (Figure 6). The first set of statistics consists of the mean velocity magnitude, mean flow angle, and second order moments for all the particles used in the simulation run, whether they pass through both beams or not. These statistics, known as global particle statistics, represent those of the input flow field itself and any deviations between them and the input flow parameters to the simulation can be attributed to the random number generators employed in the simulator. The second set of statistics, identical in form to the first set, is maintained for only those particles which the instrument sees; i.e., only those particles which successfully traverse both beams and for which a transit time has been computed. These statistics, known as instrument particle statistics, represent the global statistics of the first set convolved with the instrument transfer function and in general will be different from the global particle statistics. Any differences between the two sets of statistics reflects how well the instrument samples the flow field. Results using the analysis concepts described previously will be compared with the global particle statistics to measure the accuracy and precision of the results.

Simulation Test Matrix Results

The following test case matrix was simulated and analyzed during this study:

Mean Velocity	100.0	m/s
Flow Angle	25.0	deg
Turbulence Intensity ($=\sigma/V * 100\%$)	1.0,	%
	2.0,	
	3.0,	
	5.0,	
	7.0,	
	9.0,	
	10.0,	
	13.0,	
	15.0,	
20.0		
Correlation Coefficient	0.0,	
	0.4,	
	0.7,	
	0.9	
Beam Waist Radius	15.0	μm
Beam Separation	1230.0	μm
Bin Delay Time	96.0	nSec
Ensemble Height	50.0	
Ratio of Background Height to Ensemble Peak Height	0.00,	
	0.05,	
	0.10,	
	0.20	

The u and v components of turbulence intensity were varied equally from 1.0% to 20.0% according to the turbulence levels indicated above, and ten simulation runs were performed at each level. Each of these ten simulation cases was then analyzed using the process described previously. The results of the analysis of each run were examined to identify any failures of the processing algorithms. These cases were then removed from the test matrix, and the remaining case results were averaged. Using the averages, three types of plots were produced. First, the percent errors between analysis results and global statistics for the mean velocity and mean flow angle were computed and plotted. Next, the measured values of turbulence intensity in the u and v directions were plotted as a function of input turbulence intensity. Finally, the measured values of correlation coefficient were plotted as a function of input turbulence intensity.

In all cases the w component of the flow was set equal to zero to simulate a strictly two-dimensional flow field. However, each particle sent through the simulator had a random initial (x,y,z) position within the upstream beam's ellipsoidal loci. This process assures that the angle of acceptance of the instrument in the u, v plane is adequately simulated.

Figures 7 - 9 illustrate measured mean velocity errors as a function of input turbulence intensity and background noise height for four different values of correlation coefficient. The standard errors in the mean are illustrated as error bars around each plotted point in each figure. Note that the percent errors in mean velocity for correlation coefficients of less than 0.9 are within +2.0% for turbulence intensity levels of between 1.0% and 14.0%. These errors begin to increase rapidly at turbulence levels higher than 14.0% and reach unacceptable values for the 20.0% turbulence intensity case. Also note that the errors in mean velocity are highest for the 0.9 correlation coefficient

cases. This increase in error can be attributed to the very narrow velocity space PDFs involved in the analysis process. These narrow PDFs makes the application of equation (13) prone to errors, especially in high background noise situations.

An important trend to observe in the data present in Figures 7 - 10 is the increase in mean velocity measurement errors as a function of increasing turbulence intensity. This error may be explained by noting that as turbulence intensity increases, the spread of the correlograms in the (τ, ϕ) domain becomes wider until finally the correlograms begin to "clip" at the high end of the correlogram (at bin 255). This clipping begins to occur for a turbulence intensity level of approximately 15.0% when the peak of the correlogram is centered about bin 128. Note that clipping will not occur on the low end of the correlogram since this would imply particles having infinite velocity magnitudes in the flow. Therefore, the ultimate limitation when using the cross correlation process to measure velocity magnitudes and therefore turbulence levels is the limited range of the event correlator. The clipping of the correlogram is analogous to a data ensemble in which the peak of the (u,v) domain PDF is not adequately bracketed, as noted before. This effect causes equation (13) to provide a biased measurement.

Figures 11 - 14 illustrate the mean flow angle measurement errors as a function of input turbulence intensity and background noise height for the same correlation coefficients as were used in Figures 7 - 10. Note again that for turbulence intensities of 14.0% or less that the errors are within +2.0%. The same trends are also present in the data of Figures 11 - 14 as were present in the previous figures. The limited range of the event correlator causes equation (14) to provide a biased measurement for the same reasons discussed above. The errors introduced at high turbulence are smaller in the case of mean flow angle measurements for all values of correlation coefficient with the exception of the 0.9 coefficient case shown in Figure 14. In this case the errors become unacceptably large due to the added contributions of limited correlator range and narrowness of the PDF by the large coefficient value.

Figures 15 - 22 show the measured u and v turbulence intensities as a function of input turbulence intensity and background noise height for the same four correlation coefficients as before. Several important observations can be made from these figures. First, the standard errors in the mean are much smaller than those presented for the mean velocity and flow angle error plots. Second, the additional error introduced into the data by the addition of larger levels of background noise is negligible except for very high values of correlation coefficient and/or background noise. These two observations illustrate the ability of the elliptical fitting routines described previously to extract second order statistics from the data ensemble.

A bias error which is a function of correlation coefficient and turbulence intensity is present in the data in Figures 15 - 22. This bias error is on the order of 20.0% for an input turbulence intensity of 15.0% and a correlation coefficient of 0.9 and is smaller for lower correlation coefficient cases. This number was obtained by performing a linear fit to the data set. At this point it is not clear what is the source of this bias error, although a possible cause is that the random number generators used in the simulation system exhibit some skewness of their normal distribution when large standard deviations are being

simulated. In general, the u and v standard deviations are measurable to within +10.0% over a turbulence intensity range of 3.0% - 10.0%.

Finally, Figures 23 - 26 show the measured correlation coefficient as a function of input turbulence intensity and correlation coefficient for the four different values of background noise level used in these tests. The measurements were more accurate than was expected, since it was anticipated that great difficulty would be shown in determining the shape of the ellipse resulting from the planar cut of the (u,v) domain PDF described previously. However, there are regions in the plots where significant error are shown. For example, below approximately 3.0% the errors in correlation coefficient measurement increase significantly due the difficulty of discerning the shape of the ellipse for such narrow distributions. For similar reasons, the measurement of small correlation coefficients is the most error prone due to the fact that the ellipse becomes nearly circular in these cases making the determination of axes of the ellipse more difficult. These large errors are not acceptable since many flow fields contain correlation coefficients less than 0.4. The measured values of correlation coefficient converged to the following quantities for the different flow conditions examined.

Background to Ensemble Height Ratio	Input Correlation Coefficient	Average Measured Correlation Coefficient ($\pm 1\sigma$)
0.00	0.00	0.098 \pm 0.031
	0.40	0.372 \pm 0.039
	0.70	0.676 \pm 0.016
	0.90	0.901 \pm 0.020
0.05	0.00	0.104 \pm 0.034
	0.40	0.367 \pm 0.040
	0.70	0.679 \pm 0.020
	0.90	0.907 \pm 0.023
0.10	0.00	0.105 \pm 0.041
	0.40	0.376 \pm 0.039
	0.70	0.678 \pm 0.030
	0.90	0.906 \pm 0.019
0.20	0.00	0.124 \pm 0.052
	0.40	0.365 \pm 0.051
	0.70	0.682 \pm 0.022
	0.90	0.914 \pm 0.022

Conclusions

A Monte Carlo based LTA simulation system has been used to perform a detailed evaluation of a set of processing algorithms proposed by Mayo and Smart for the extraction of two dimensional flow parameters from LTA data sets collected in a plane normal to the optical axis of the system. This specific work concentrated on testing the ability of these algorithms to accurately extract flow parameters from data sets containing various amount of Poisson distributed background noise in the constituent correlograms. In general, the results indicate that the algorithms have adequate correlogram noise

rejection capability for turbulence intensity levels of up to approximately 10.0%. However, at higher turbulence intensity levels significant errors begin to appear in the measured flow parameters which may be unacceptable in some situations. Further refinement of the processing algorithms may reduce some of these errors. In all, the LTA processing system described here has a number of useful applications when full two dimensional flow parameters are desired during a flow field survey, but care must be taken in using them to minimize errors and to properly interpret the results.

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Figure 1. Cartesian Velocity Space PDF for a Typical Set of Flow Parameters.

Figure 2. Correlogram Ensembles in (τ, θ) and (u,v) Space.

Figure 3. Top View of Projection on (u,v) Plane Shown in Figure 2b.

Figure 4. Monte-Carlo Simulation Sample Volume Model.

Figure 5. Sample Correlograms With 0% and 10% Poisson Distributed Background Noise.

- A - Desired flow parameters and particle statistics
- B - Global particle ensemble and statistics
- C - Instrument particle ensemble and statistics
(Consists only of particles detected by downstream beam)
- D - Measured flow parameters and particle statistics from analysis

Figure 6. Simulation - Analysis Loop Showing Statistics Maintained by Simulator.

Figure 7. Mean Velocity Measurement Errors as a Function of Input Turbulence and Background Height. Input $\rho = 0.0$.

Figure 10. Mean Velocity Measurement Errors as a Function of Input Turbulence and Background Height. Input $\rho = 0.9$.

Figure 8. Mean Velocity Measurement Errors as a Function of Input Turbulence and Background Height. Input $\rho = 0.4$.

Figure 11. Mean Flow Angle Measurement Errors as a Function of Input Turbulence and Background Height. Input $\rho = 0.0$.

Figure 9. Mean Velocity Measurement Errors as a Function of Input Turbulence and Background Height. Input $\rho = 0.7$.

Figure 12. Mean Flow Angle Measurement Errors as a Function of Input Turbulence and Background Height. Input $\rho = 0.4$.

Figure 13. Mean Flow Angle Measurement Errors as a Function of Input Turbulence and Background Height. Input $\rho = 0.7$.

Figure 14. Mean Flow Angle Measurement Errors as a Function of Input Turbulence and Background Height. Input $\rho = 0.9$.

Figure 15. Deviation of Measured u Turbulence Intensity from Ideal Instrument Case as a Function of Input Turbulence and Background Height. Input $\rho = 0.0$.

Figure 16. Deviation of Measured u Turbulence Intensity from Ideal Instrument Case as a Function of Input Turbulence and Background Height. Input $\rho = 0.4$.

Figure 17. Deviation of Measured u Turbulence Intensity from Ideal Instrument Case as a Function of Input Turbulence and Background Height. Input $\rho = 0.7$.

Figure 18. Deviation of Measured u Turbulence Intensity from Ideal Instrument Case as a Function of Input Turbulence and Background Height. Input $\rho = 0.9$.

Figure 19. Deviation of Measured v Turbulence Intensity from Ideal Instrument Case as a Function of Input Turbulence and Background Height. Input $\rho = 0.0$.

Figure 22. Deviation of Measured v Turbulence Intensity from Ideal Instrument Case as a Function of Input Turbulence and Background Height. Input $\rho = 0.9$.

Figure 20. Deviation of Measured v Turbulence Intensity from Ideal Instrument Case as a Function of Input Turbulence and Background Height. Input $\rho = 0.4$.

Figure 23. Measured Correlation Coefficient as a Function of Input Turbulence for 0% Correlogram Background.

Figure 21. Deviation of Measured v Turbulence Intensity from Ideal Instrument Case as a Function of Input Turbulence and Background Height. Input $\rho = 0.7$.

Figure 24. Measured Correlation Coefficient as a Function of Input Turbulence for 5% Correlogram Background.

Figure 25. Measured Correlation Coefficient as a Function of Input Turbulence for 10% Correlogram Background.

Figure 26. Measured Correlation Coefficient as a Function of Input Turbulence for 20% Correlogram Background.